

Effect Of Solid Piggery Sludge Application on Soil Properties, Cowpea Production, and Tissue Accumulation of Metals under Humid Tropical Lowland Conditions in Papua New Guinea

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Abstract

The production of solid piggery sludge (SPS) in Papua New Guinea (PNG) has increased, and there is a need to manage it to avoid environmental concerns. In this study, we investigated the potential use of SPS in cowpea production as a legume to enhance soil health and as a raw material for livestock feed and human food. A replicated field trial with four rates of amendments (0, 2.5, 5.0, and 10 t ha⁻¹) as treatments was conducted under field conditions by planting cowpea. Each treatment was replicated five times (n=5) and set up in a completely randomized block design. After six months of production, the whole plants were uprooted, and the total number of plants and root nodules were counted; and plant height, leaf length, and root length were measured. At the same time, 3 kg of soil samples were collected from the spots where the plants were harvested and packed. All the samples were taken to the laboratory and processed for minerals (nutrients and metals) analysis. The whole plants were oven-dried for dry matter, and leaf and root weights. The averages of all the parameters were obtained by taking the mean of the replicates (n=4). Significant differences (p<0.05) between the treatment means were compared by two-way ANOVA, and if interaction between the treatments and profile depth was found, one-way ANOVA with all combinations was performed using Tukey's HSD (honestly significant difference) and pairwise comparisons. The overall results showed that all the soil parameters except pH and texture were significantly improved. At the highest amendment rate, the primary macronutrients N, P, and K were increased by 92%, 133%, and 200%, respectively. The secondary macronutrients and most of the micronutrients were increased significantly as well. The highest dry matter (86%) was produced by the 5.0 t ha⁻¹ amendment, and Zn, Mn, Al, Fe, and Cr accumulated in the biomass. Comparatively, Cd, Ni, and Pb in soil and Cd, Cr, Cu, and Pb in biomass were higher than the standard FAO permissible levels of metals. This study showed that agricultural use of SPS has the potential to improve general soil health and increase cowpea production by an amendment rate of 5.0 t ha⁻¹ in the humid tropics. A rate of 10 t ha⁻¹ was detrimental to cowpea production and to livestock and human beings' health.

Keywords: Bioaccumulation factors, heavy metals, humid tropical lowland, PNG, piggery sludge, soil amendment, soil fertility, *Vigna unguiculata*.

Introduction

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L.) is a legume widely cultivated in the tropics because of its socio-economic and nutraceutical importance (Singh et al., 2002) and many other places in the world (Antova et al., 2014). These make cowpea one of the multifunctional crops as food for humans and livestock, income generating commodity for farmers, and a raw material for the industries (Gonçalves et al., 2016; Abebe et al., 2022). On estimation, 5.8 million tons of dry cowpea cereal are produced in 11 million ha of land, with an output of 527 kg ha⁻¹ (Xiong et al., 2016). As a legume, cowpea fixes a lot of nitrogen into the soil, e.g., 100 kg ha⁻¹ (Rangel and Silva, 2007), and is an excellent substitute for inorganic (chemical) fertilizers for agricultural and environmental sustainability. Inclusion of cowpea, for example, in crop rotation with a non-leguminous crop increases organic matter and improves soil fertility (nutrients), water infiltration and retention, soil microbial activity, and other soil parameters such as pH, electrical conductivity, bulk density, total porosity, cation exchange capacity, and base saturation (Michael, 2019a; 2021). Cowpea is highly stable and tolerant to environmental stresses (drought, salinity, high temperature) and has wider adaptability, making it one of the most widely cultivated legumes in the world (Langyintuo et al., 2003; Guerra et al., 2017).

In developing countries like PNG, where the supply of sources of a balanced diet is low, edible legumes such as peas (*Pisium sativum* L.), peanuts (*Arachis hypogea* L.), beans (*Phaseolus* spp.), and cowpea are an important source of food and nutritional security. Even in the developed countries, cowpea is an important and alternative source of protein as well as other nutritional requirements, low in fat and high in edible fibre, contributing to the health and well-being of the consumers (Timko et al., 2008). As a food source, the mature beans, green pods, and leaves are used as food and as ingredients in the food industries (Frota et al., 2008; Xu and Chang, 2012; Kapravelou et al., 2015; Bello et al., 2017). In terms of human and livestock diet, cowpea is a chief source of carbohydrates, protein, and fats as primary nutrients (energy), minerals, vitamins, and fibre as micronutrients and bioactive compounds (Giami, 2005). Several studies showed cowpea is nutritionally high in macronutrients in protein (e.g., Carvalho et al., 2012; Boye et al., 2012; Santos et al., 2013), carbohydrate (e.g., Phillips et al., 2003; Williams et al., 2008; Vasconcelos et al., 2010), and lipids (e.g., Asare et al., 2013; Antova et al., 2014). In terms of micronutrients, cowpea is an essential source of all the seventeen minerals and thirteen vitamins required to prevent malnutrition and nutritional disorders (DellaPenna, 1999). Nutraceutical compounds are components of food that contribute to critical physiological functions in human and livestock health and range from dietary fibre, probiotics, prebiotics, polyunsaturated fatty acids, antioxidant vitamins, and phenolic compounds. All of these nutraceutical compounds have been reported in cowpea in a range of concentrations (e.g., Das et al., 2012).

Uses of cowpea in management of degraded agricultural land by symbiotic nitrogen fixation potential (e.g., Ruiz-de-Cenzano et al., 2015; Mganga et al., 2016) important for management of soil nutrients and ecological stability are well document. In large-scale production, especially in poor soil, the nutrient requirements of cowpea range from 20 – 25 kg ha⁻¹ N, 40 – 50 P kg ha⁻¹, and 20 – 25 kg ha⁻¹ (primary macronutrients) and micronutrients such as zinc, iron, and boron. In principle, these nutrient requirements are met through application of inorganic (chemical fertilizers) or organic amendments. In the developing and underdeveloped economies, the availability of inorganic fertilizers is limited to certain places

(towns and cities), and affordability continues to be an issue for small farmers because the costs are often high, making yield to be low and unpredictable (Bakshi et al., 2025). We have shown in several studies that the use of organic matter as soil amendment under various land use conditions is an important option (e.g., Michael, 2019b). Organic amendments provide humus for soil structure stability, drainage, aeration, water holding capacity, mineral solubility, and are an essential energy substrate for soil microbes (Christina et al., 2024). In addition, there is a consensus that organic amendment lowers the cultivation costs and lessen the environmental impacts of chemical fertilizers (Debbarma et al., 2020; Owade et al., 2020; Abebe et al., 2022; Simon et al., 2025).

The different sources of organic amendments include green manure, vermicompost, oil cake, farmyard manure (several in the form of cattle, poultry, goat, sheep, slaughter house trash, crop stumbles and harvesting trashes and so on), and wastes in the form of effluents from processing plants (e.g., oil palm mills) and farm wastes stabilisation ponds (e.g. piggery effluent ponds). These different sources of organic amendments have different soil conditioning properties and application potentials under cowpea production, yet there are limited studies for wider publicity.

Wang et al. (2025) reported that the application of organic fertilizer improved soil physiochemical properties, microbial community structure, and yield of cowpea. The yield of cowpea was increased when grown in soil amended with organic matter (Wang et al., 2025), and similar results were obtained by Darsiah et al. (2021) in soil amended with manure. Subedi et al. (2022) reported high cowpea yield (8.44 t ha^{-1}) in soil amended with poultry manure compared to goat and farmyard manure. Adeoye et al. (2011) stated that poultry and cattle manure use as soil amendment gave similar cowpea yield, just as the finding of Ogunkunle et al. (2023), who found increased and improved general plant growth of cowpea under poultry manure application.

An increasing number of research findings available in the public domain (e.g., Randall et al., 2006; Kyei-Boahen et al., 2017) show that addition of organic matter sources of plant and animal origin improves soil biological, chemical and physical properties and enhances the general growth and development of cowpea (e.g., Olusegun, 2014; Bada et al., 2015; Deepa et al., 2016; Gonçalves et al., 2016; Yogananda et al., 2019; Mfeka et al., 2019; Issoufa et al., 2020; Emmanuel et al., 2020; Osipitan et al., 2021; Sánchez-Navarro et al., 2021; Diatta et al., 2024; Bondok et al., 2024; Bala et al., 2024; da Costa et al., 2024; Ferreira et al., 2025). One other important source of organic matter that received little attention is the use of SPS as soil amendment and cowpea production although there are evidences of findings of studies using pig manure under cowpea production (Olusegun, 2014; Ojo et al., 2020; Atugwu et al., 2023). This study was conducted to investigate the effects of SPS as an amendment on soil properties under cowpea production in the lowland tropical humid tropics and potential tissue accumulation from a general use perspective.

Materials and Methods

Description of study land

The study was conducted at PNGUoT Agriculture Farm ($6^{\circ}41'' \text{ S}$, $146^{\circ}98'' \text{ E}$) in Lae, Morobe Province, PNG, at 65 m elevation, described in many publications (e.g., Michael, 2019a; b; 2020a; b; c; d). The climate has 3800 mm annual rainfall, evenly spread, with mean

temperature of 26.3°C, min 22.9°C, max 29.7°C. Evaporation is 2139 mm annually, with rainfall exceeding evaporation each month. Climate is Af (Köppen), a tropical rainy climate with >60 mm driest month. The soil is well-drained, sandy, alluvial, classified as Typic Tropofluents or Eutric Fluvisol. Selected soil parameters, nutrients, and metal contents of the site are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Soil parameters of the farm soil, SPS and expected range in the amended soils.

Soil parameters	Composition of parameters of the farm soil and the SPS		
	Farm (study site)	SPS	Range
Soil organic matter (SOM, %)	2.59±0.1	22.17±0.1	3 – 22
Soil organic carbon (SOC, %)	1.50±0.0	12.76±0.8	2 – 13
pH	6.50±0.1	6.80±0.6	6 – 7
Cation exchange capacity (meq/100 g)	7.23	–	–
Base saturation (BS, %)	65.30±0.5	11.76±0.2	6.5 – 12
Electrical conductivity (EC, mS m ⁻¹)	0.03±0.1	1.92±1.2	0 – 2
Water holding capacity (WHC, %)	54.25±1.0	53.71±0.6	54 – 54
Bulk density (BD, g cm ⁻³)	1.12±0.0	0.60±0.1	0.6 – 1
Total porosity (TP, %)	52.02±0.6	56.02±1.2	52 – 56
Particle composition (SPC, %)			
(a) Sand	89.982±0.0	83.13±0.0	83 – 90
(b) Silt	0.45±0.0	4.01±0.1	0.5 – 4
(c) Clay	9.63±0.0	12.83±0.0	10 – 13
N (mg kg ⁻¹)	1500±0.2	17,600±20.3	15,000 – 18,000
P (mg kg ⁻¹)	10.62±0.3	49.62±1.1	11 – 50
K (mg kg ⁻¹)	20.73±0.3	145.94±4.9	21 – 146
Mg (mg kg ⁻¹)	131.28±5.7	666.02±10.6	131 – 670
Ca (mg kg ⁻¹)	732.11±5.6	2,643.27±54.5	732 – 2,640
S (mg kg ⁻¹)	6.52±0.7	144.24±0.8	7 – 144
Na (mg kg ⁻¹)	14.32±0.5	62.72±2.3	14 – 63
Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	507.38±0.2	72.89±0.50.2	73 – 507
B (mg kg ⁻¹)	8.82±0.8	18.01±0.9	9 – 18
Mn (mg kg ⁻¹)	46.30±0.6	191.17±0.5	46 – 191
Al (mg kg ⁻¹)	270.67±1.1	9.23±1.3	9 – 271
Cd (mg kg ⁻¹)	6.62±0.2*	12.67±0.3*	7 – 13
Ni (mg kg ⁻¹)	70.61±0.8*	43.73±0.7	44 – 71
Pb (mg kg ⁻¹)	730.56±1.3*	4.43±0.2	4 – 731
Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)	89.56±1.1	439.14±1.5	90 – 439
Cr (mg kg ⁻¹)	96.08±0.1	21.19±0.7	21 – 96
Co (mg kg ⁻¹)	<5.12±0.0	<5.21±0.0	<5
Cu (mg kg ⁻¹)	257.82±2.3*	65.09±0.2	65 – 258

The values are means of three replicate samples ± standard error. Note, range is the expected change in the amended soils. An asterisk shows concentrations higher than FAO permissible limits of agricultural soil, however, the farm is within a residential area and the concentrations maybe considered permissible.

Collection and preparation of piggery sludge

Solid treated piggery sludge was collected from a stockpile from a commercial piggery farm outside of Lae City and brought to the farm for use. The samples were dried on canvas under direct sunlight for a week and weighed using an electric scale. The dried sludge samples were packed into 1000 g, 500 g, and 250 g polyester bags and kept dry before field applications. An analysis of soil parameters, nutrients, and metal contents of the SPS is shown in Table 1.

Sourcing of planting materials

Cowpea (*V. unguiculata*) was chosen as the target plant and planted as it is essential for various industries as raw materials for feed production for livestock, as well as food for human consumption in PNG. The seeds were sourced from local suppliers within Lae City, Morobe Province, PNG.

Land preparation and setting of experiment

A piece of land (17 m x 13 m; 221 m²) on the farm was ploughed and harrowed using a tractor (Messy Ferguson, Germany). A total of 96 experimental plots (1 m x 1 m) were prepared, separated by a 0.5 m spacing within and between plots. There were four treatments: control (planted with no amendment), 2.5 (lowest), 5 (high), and 10 (highest) t ha⁻¹ of SPS. All the treatments were replicated five times (n=5) and arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD). The SPS was applied to the soil surface and manually incorporated using handheld shovels into the top 30 cm.

Planting and production management

Based on germination test results, fifteen seeds of cowpea were sown. Throughout the four months of running the study, watering, weeding, and pest and disease control were carried out as per the farm's general practice. There was no thinning done to the plants.

Field Sampling and preparations

Sampling and yield related parameter assessment

All the biomasses (above and below ground) sampled from all the treatment plots. Soil and root samples were collected from the top 30 cm rhizosphere or a 10 cm radius of the plants. Each plant was gently uprooted with minimum root disturbance using a handheld shovel. The soil with the intact roots was carefully shaken onto a canvas and homogenized by mixing before collecting 3 kg of soil subsample per replicate or 12 kg per treatment, and bagged into pre-labelled paper bags. The shoot and root biomasses were chopped into 1–2 cm long pieces using a gardener's clipper and bagged in pre-labelled plastic bags. All the samples were transported to the laboratory for further processing (cleaning, washing, and oven-drying).

Sample preparations

At the laboratory, the roots were gently washed under tap water to remove excess soil, and the fresh weight was taken. Then the samples were air-dried at room temperature for 24 hours, and all the leaves, stems, vines, and roots were chopped into 1-2 cm long pieces using kitchen knives, packed into paper bags, and oven-dried at 65 °C for three days to determine dry matter (yields). The dry samples were then ground using a food blender, packed into resealable bags, and kept dry to analyse the mineral content. The soil samples from the field were transferred to aluminium trays and air-dried at room temperature for 7 days, and then

sieved into 0.05 mm, 0.5 mm, and 2.0 mm for different measurements and analyses at the PNGUoT Analytica Laboratory.

Laboratory analysis of parameters

Important soil physical and chemical properties that influence soil fertility, mineral, and nutrient availability were determined according to Michael (2020a; b; c; d). Ground biomasses were analysed using laboratory analytical equipment, and the standard equations (Eqn. 1 to 10) were used to assess. Total nitrogen was analysed by the Kjeldahl method (Buchi K436 speed digester and Buchi K-350 Kjeldahl distillation unit). A sample of one-gram (< 2 mm) air-dried soil was digested using 15 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid at 300 – 400 °C (H₂SO₄ reduces nitrogen as ammonium sulphate (NH₄)₂SO₄). The sample solution was distilled using 60% sodium hydroxide (NaOH), where ammonium (NH₄⁺) was converted to ammonia (NH₃) gas, which was collected using 25 ml of 2% boric acid with three drops of mixed indicator. It was then back-titrated with 0.01 M HCl. The available nitrogen (NO₃-N) was determined using the salicylic acid method with UV light after extraction with 0.027 M Ca(OH)₂. The available P was determined by Olsen using a spectrophotometer (UV1800, Shimadzu Corporation, Japan) using 0.5 M sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃) after adjusting the pH to 8.5 with NaOH. Extraction was for 30 minutes using a 200-rpm shaker at a soil-to-extraction solution ratio of 1:20 (w/v).

All the other nutrients (K, Mg, Na, Ca, S, Mn, Zn, B, Cu, Fe, and Al) were extracted with a Melich 3 extraction solution (0.2 M CH₃COOH + 0.25 M NH₄NO₃ + 0.015 M NH₄F + 0.13 M HNO₃ + 0.001 M EDTA) in 1:10 (soil: extractant ratio) and analysed using an ICP OES. The data was calculated as per Melich3 18F1 standard as follows:

$$N = ((C - B) \times (Ve \div Ws)) \quad (1)$$

Where N is nutrient, e.g., K, C is concentration, B is blank ((mg element/dm³), Ve is effective volume used in the extraction calculation (1:20 soil to solution), and Ws is the weight of the sample, respectively. The data in milli-equivalent (mEq./100 g soil) were converted to milligrams (mg) as follows:

$$mg = [(mEq \times Aw) \div V] \quad (2)$$

Where Aw is the atomic weight of an element (e.g., nitrogen) and V is valence, respectively. Cation exchange capacity (CEC) was estimated based on the sum of the individual base cations (Ca, Mg, K and Na) as follows:

$$CEC = \left(\frac{\text{Sum of bases}}{\text{Base saturation \%}} \right) 100 \quad (3)$$

Sum of bases are in meq/100g and are individual exchangeable base cations. Based saturation (%) is from the soil analysis data (e.g., Table 5).

Soil moisture content was determined by oven-drying samples at 105 °C for 24 hours, and the final weight was estimated after 2 hours of cooling by subtracting the dry weight from the initial fresh weight.

The pH was measured using a standard dilution (1:5 soil: water w/v) method (Michael, 2019b). Electrical conductivity was measured using a Direct Soil EC meter (Spectrum

Technologies Inc., 12360S Industrial Dr. East Plainfield, IL 60585, USA), using the same solutions (Michael, 2020a; b; c).

The bulk density (g cm^{-3}) was calculated by oven-drying the cores at 105 °C for 48 hours, followed by weighing again (Michael, 2020d). The oven dry weights were divided by the core volume and estimated as follows:

$$BD = (\text{Odw} \div \pi r^2 h) \quad (4)$$

Where BD is bulk density (g cm^{-3}), Odw is oven dry weight and formula for estimation of the volume of the core.

The soil organic carbon (SOC) content was analyzed using the weight loss-on-ignition method. A five-gram sample was weighed into a crucible and heated in a muffle furnace for 12 hours at 105 °C (Wf). The weights were recorded after 2 hours of cooling, further combusted at 375 °C for 17 hours (Fw), cooled for 2 hours, and weighed (Michael, 2019a).

The SOC content was estimated by multiplying the carbon value by a conversion factor (1.72) and expressed as a percentage:

$$\text{SOC (\%)} = [((\text{Wf} - \text{Fw}) \div \text{Wf}) \div 1.724]100 \text{ or } (\text{SOM (\%)} \div 1.724) \quad (5)$$

The conversion factor was used to convert the soil organic matter content to organic C, assuming there was 58% C in the organic matter.

The size of the C stock in each profile was calculated as the sum of the individual C fractions (%) \times BD (g cm^{-3}) \times profile depth (SP, cm) \times Cf and expressed as a percentage as per Michael (2020) as follows:

$$\text{SOC}_{\text{stock}} (\%) = [((\text{SOC}/100) \times \text{BD} \times \text{SP}) \times \text{Cf}] \quad (6)$$

Where SOC was determined using Eqn. 4 and the Cf obtained by $100 \div 58$. The soil organic matter (SOM) contents were estimated using the SOC content and the conversion factor as follows:

$$\text{SOM (\%)} = [(\text{SOC}) \times \text{Cf}] \quad (7)$$

The water holding capacity (WHC) was estimated by soaking soil samples in water (100% WHC) and draining them through filter paper overnight (e.g., Michael, 2019a). These were weighed for the wet weight (W_w), dried in an oven at 105 °C for 24 hours, and reweighed to obtain the oven-dry weight (OD_w). The WHC was estimated as follows:

$$\text{WHC (\%)} = [((\text{W}_w - \text{OD}_w) \div \text{OD}_w) 100] \quad (8)$$

The total porosity was determined as follows:

$$P = \left[\left(1 - \frac{BD}{d} \right) \right] 100 \quad (9)$$

Where P is total porosity (%), BD was defined and d is particle density of 2.65 g cm^{-3} .

The weight of the SOM to a given depth and area was estimated as follows:

$$\text{SOM (tons)} = [(\text{SOC} \times \text{BD} \times \text{SP} \times \text{ha}) 1.72] \quad (10)$$

Where SOC is in %, BD is in g cm^{-3} , SP is in m and ha is hectare ($10\,000 \text{ m}^2$).

The bioaccumulation factors (BiF) were calculated as follows:

$$\text{BiF} = \left(\frac{\text{Mpt}}{\text{Ms}} \right) \quad (11)$$

Where Mpt is metal concentrations of plant tissues and Ms is metal concentration in the soil. Values >1 indicate metal accumulation, whereas values <1 suggest limited uptake or exclusion mechanisms.

Statistical analysis

Data from four replicates of all the treatments were used for statistical analysis and the samples from the fifth replicate were kept frozen as reserves to cater for losses due to mishandling of samples or related issues. The replicated data were used to calculate the treatment means and standard errors. Assumptions of normality (Shapiro-Wilk test) and homogeneity of variance (Levene's test) were tested for each response variable and the data were log-transformed where necessary to meet assumptions.

This was followed by a two-way ANOVA with pasture and amendment rate as fixed factors to test for main effects and interactions. When significant interactions were detected ($p < 0.05$), one-way ANOVA with significant treatment effects, and Tukey's HSD post hoc test for pairwise comparisons was used. All analyses were conducted using JMP Pro 16 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA).

Results and Discussion

Changes in soil properties

The SOM contents of the farm soil was within a range (2%) of typical sandy loam soil (Table 1). When the SPS with 22% SOM was added, the content of the amended soils significantly increased, with the highest being measured from the highest rate, the increase being nearly 5.87% (Table 2). That is almost 59 g SOM kg⁻¹ soil. In the control soil, 12 g C kg⁻¹ soil was measured (Table 2) compared to the 15 g C kg⁻¹ in the farm soil (Table 1).

The general trend in the SOC contents was similar to the SOM contents, the changes ranging from 27 g C kg⁻¹ to 80 g C kg⁻¹ (see Table 4). For example, when the rate of amendment was 2.5 t ha⁻¹, the SOC increase was 15 g C kg⁻¹ and it increased to 6.76% by the highest rate (Table 2). SOC is generally 58% of the SOM and is important for various ecological services (e.g., Michael, 2021).

These results showed SPS is important to SOM and SOC contents, as well as the other soil properties. There was not much change in the soil pH, and it remained within a preferable range of 5.5–7.0. Soil moisture and WHC were also improved by higher rates.

Table 2. Changes in soil properties under bean production.

Parameters	The different rates of the amendment (t ha ⁻¹)					
	0	2.50	5.00	10.00		
SOM (%)	2.05±0.1 ^a	3.82±0.6 ^a	5.21±0.9 ^b	7.87±0.1 ^c		
SOC (%)	1.19±0.0 ^a	2.65±0.1 ^b	4.69±0.1 ^c	7.95±0.6 ^d		
pH	6.50±0.6 ^a	6.53±0.9 ^a	6.40±0.0 ^a	6.60±0.0 ^a		
Moisture (%)	7.52±0.8 ^a	7.72±0.2 ^a	8.32±0.5 ^b	9.34±0.7 ^{cb}		
WHC (%)	62.15±0.9 ^a	66.83±0.8 ^a	70.13±0.1 ^b	75.63±0.6 ^{bc}		
BS (%)	65.70±0.8 ^a	67.83±0.8 ^a	69.13±0.6 ^a	73.63±0.6 ^b		
CEC (meq/100 g)	6.51±1.11 ^a	7.79±0.25 ^a	10.92±1.12 ^b	12.27±2.21 ^{bc}		
EC (mS m ⁻¹)	150.21±0.5 ^a	160.32±0.0 ^b	175.22±0.2 ^c	186.66±0.0 ^{dc}		
BD (g cm ⁻³)	1.21±0.2 ^a	1.13±0.6 ^a	1.12±0.5 ^a	1.11±0.1 ^a		
TP (%)	36.02±0.5 ^a	40.22±1.1 ^a	43.23±1.1 ^b	44.44±1.3 ^{bc}		
SPC (%)	Clay	10.99±0.5 ^a	9.87±0.4 ^a	10.01±0.2 ^a	9.86±0.6 ^a	
		Silt	2.64±0.3 ^a	0.45±0.5 ^b	0.46±0.2 ^{bc}	0.46±0.5 ^{bd}
		Sand	86.37±0.2 ^a	89.68±0.5 ^a	89.53±0.0 ^a	89.68±0.5 ^a

The values are mean ± standard error of four replicates (n=4). The different letters within a row indicate statistical differences at p<0.05. The acronyms have been described in Table 1.

The changes measured in BS, EC, BD, TP, and SPC were positively influenced by the higher amendment rates, the most significant changes being induced by 10 t ha⁻¹ (Table 2). Notably, TP decreased under the highest amendment rate, and this seems to have been caused by the weight of the amendment rather than the texture (sand, silt, and clay composition). The soil texture remained nearly unchanged, and that was reflected in the soil moisture content. Soil moisture level decreased SPC increased. The general changes in the soil properties measured reflected on the SOM contents, and more so the SOC that is associated with it. Various researchers have pointed out that the improvement in SOC from organic matter, such as the SPS, affects aggregate stability (Bronick and Lal, 2005), cation exchange capacity, nutrient cycling, nitrogen mineralization (Weil and Bradley, 2017), microbial activity with C as a carbon source (Poeplau and Don, 2015; Schloter et al., 2018), and nutrient use efficiency, and yield (Franzluebbers, 2010). Han et al. (2018), for example, showed that an increase in SOC by 0.1% (10 g C kg⁻¹) could lead to 4.0 to 6.6 bushels per acre per year of yield (biomass). In this study, an increase of 8 g C kg⁻¹ soil resulted in dry matter production of 51 g, a 59.30% increase compared to the control (biomass data, Table 5).

Changes in soil mineral and metal compositions

The farm soil had a certain level of nutrients, the highest being N (Table 1). Following the amendments, all the primary and secondary macronutrients increased with an increase in rate of amendments (Table 3). Addition of 2.5 t ha⁻¹ increased N by 15.39%, 53.85% by 5.00 t ha⁻¹, and by 92.31% by 10 t ha⁻¹. A proportionate increase in all the other primary and secondary macronutrients was measured in all the amended soils. The soil S experienced a steady increase, ranging from 10–52 mg kg⁻¹ as well (Table 3). Most of the trace elements (the heavy metals and Al) were significantly high in all the soils amended with high rates. Compared to the contents of the original soil and SPS (Table 1), elements like B, Pb, Ni, Cr, and Co contents were unchanged or decreased. The overall changes in the compositions of

metals, except for Cd, Ni, and Pb, were within the maximum permissible limits of agricultural soils (Table 3). Cd, Ni, and Pb are highly toxic soil pollutants and cause severe environmental damage, including soil degradation, soil quality impairment, and impaired water quality. These metals bioaccumulate in organisms and are potential threats to crops, livestock, and humans through food chains.

Table 3. Changes in soil mineral and metal compositions under bean production.

Elements (mg kg ⁻¹)	The different rates of the amendment (t ha ⁻¹)				Permissible (FAO/WHO)
	0.0	2.5	5.0	10.0	
N	1300.21±0.1 ^a	1500.11±0.0 ^b	2000.22±0.0 ^c	2500.32±0.1 ^d	
P	8.47±0.1 ^a	10.53±0.1 ^a	13.32±0.1 ^{ab}	20.46±0.1 ^c	
K	18.08±0.5 ^a	22.27±0.5 ^a	35.21±0.5 ^b	54.44±0.4 ^c	
Ca	610.21±1.4 ^a	734.33±5.0 ^b	1080.01±6.8 ^c	1137.33±7.9 ^d	
Mg	129.84±3.2 ^a	174.33±1.5 ^b	226.00±2.3 ^c	347.33±1.5 ^d	
Na	12.33±1.4 ^a	25.98±1.8 ^b	41.45±1.2 ^c	55.14±1.2 ^{cd}	
S	4.03±0.2 ^a	14.24±0.2 ^b	34.63±0.2 ^c	56.74±0.2 ^d	
B	6.89±0.9 ^a	11.53±0.9 ^a	13.62±0.8 ^{ab}	16.21±0.0 ^{bc}	
Mn	39.33±0.8 ^a	47.87±0.9 ^b	55.76±0.6 ^{bc}	67.9±0.9 ^{cd}	
Cu	57.28±0.4 ^a	62.24±0.7 ^a	75.48±0.9 ^b	109.32±0.7 ^{bc}	36 – 100
Zn	53.11±0.2 ^a	67.44±0.4 ^b	80.03±0.7 ^c	87.93±0.1 ^{cd}	50 – 300
Fe	410.67±1.5 ^a	449.67±1.5 ^a	468.15±1.1 ^{ab}	514.52±1.7 ^{bc}	50,000
Cd*	3.24±0.1 ^a	6.96±0.3 ^b	12.60±0.1 ^c	17.01±0.0 ^d	3.0
Ni*	47.49±1.4 ^a	58.63±0.9 ^b	67.92±1.5 ^{bc}	91.16±1.3 ^d	35 – 50
Pb*	511.01±1.2 ^a	547.39±0.5 ^b	608.85±1.4 ^c	692.64±1.6 ^{cd}	85 – 100
Cr	41.77±1.6 ^a	52.77±1.9 ^b	63.48±2.5 ^c	75.02±2.1 ^d	100.0
Co	0.06±0.0 ^a	0.07±0.0 ^a	0.05±0.0 ^a	0.08±0.1 ^a	50.0
Al	133.26±1.1 ^a	140.22±1.2 ^a	152.50±1.4 ^b	161.66±2.0 ^{bc}	≤30,000

The values are mean ± standard error of four replicates (n=4). The different letters within a row indicate statistical differences at p<0.05. An asterisk shows concentrations higher than FAO/WHO permissible limits of agricultural soils.

Some of these minerals, whose concentrations decreased, would mean tissue accumulation and are a concern for the livestock, humans, and the environment (discussed hereunder). For example, the Pb content of the soil was expected to be 730 mg kg⁻¹; however, there was 511 mg kg⁻¹ in the unamended soil, and that was increased by 36 mg kg⁻¹ when 2.5 t ha⁻¹ was added to the soil. The highest amendment rate resulted in an increase of 181 mg kg⁻¹ (Table 3), supporting the assumption that the need for Pb is minimal or tissue accumulation. The Al in the control soil (Table 3) was less than what was available in the farm soil (Table 3), but as the amendment rates were higher, there was more in the soil. Overall, the results showed that SPS amendment of soil for cowpea production is important for the macronutrients as well as the trace elements essential to the plants. The heavy metals, Al, and the rest of the trace elements were within the FAO maximum limits of dangerous substances in soil, except Pb, which was higher than 50 mg kg⁻¹ (Table 3). The Pb concentration in the soil measured was even higher than the expected residential value of 300 mg kg⁻¹ (Flora et al.,

2012; Assi et al., 2016) and therefore is a concern from human beings and livestock health perspectives.

Metal concentrations in biomass

The metal concentrations of the unamended soil were high (Pb>Al>Cu>Fe>Cr>Zn>Ni), and those of the others less than 10 mg kg⁻¹ (Table 4). In the 2.5 t ha⁻¹ amended soils, all the heavy metal concentrations increased significantly except for Co and Cr, which were not significant (Zn>Cu>Mn>Al>Fe>Pb>the rest). The tissue compositions of 5–10 t ha⁻¹ of all the metals generally decreased. The highest decrease in concentrations of the metals depended on the concentrations of the unamended soil and the sludge. The changes in tissue concentrations were the opposite of those of Zn and Mn, which were high throughout. Comparatively, only Cd, Cr, Cu, and Pb concentrations were higher than the maximum permissible limits of crops (Table 4). These metals are highly toxic to plants, thereby inhibiting growth and reducing biomass. As pointed out above, these metals bioaccumulate and are potential threats to livestock and human health.

Table 4. Metal concentrations in biomass at different rates of amendments.

Metals (mg kg ⁻¹)	Different rates of amendments (t ha ⁻¹)				Permissible (FAO/WHO)
	0.0	2.5	5.00	10.00	
Al	151.44±0.4 ^a	128.54±0.3 ^b	124.44±0.6 ^{ab}	99.33±0.2 ^c	(–)
Cd*	3.52±0.5 ^a	12.55±0.6 ^b	6.53±0.6 ^{ac}	2.22±0.2 ^{ad}	0.1 – 0.2
Co	4.32±0.5 ^a	4.11±0.5 ^a	3.99±0.5 ^a	3.89±0.8 ^a	50.0
Cr*	52.23±0.1 ^a	62.99±0.2 ^a	50.11±0.4 ^a	40.24±0.6 ^b	1.3 – 1.5
Cu*	186.24±0.2 ^a	258.66±0.6 ^b	245.54±0.3 ^{ab}	211.46±0.5 ^{bc}	73.0
Fe	95.45±0.8 ^a	127.25±0.4 ^b	109.62±0.4 ^{ac}	63.22±0.2 ^{ad}	425.0
Ni	18.66±0.4 ^a	39.33±0.4 ^b	35.45±0.7 ^{bc}	12.29±0.1 ^{ad}	67.0
Pb*	215.66±0.7 ^a	112.22±0.2 ^b	122.32±0.5 ^{bc}	39.54±0.2 ^d	0.3 – 2
Zn	34.67±0.4 ^a	455.66±0.1 ^b	439.21±0.6 ^{bc}	438.21±0.4 ^{bd}	99.4 – 500
Mn	6.65±0.5 ^a	176.55±0.6 ^b	180.54±0.2 ^{bc}	167.84±0.2 ^{bd}	500.0

The values are mean ± standard error of four replicates (n=4). The different letters within a row indicate statistical differences at p<0.05. An asterisk shows concentrations higher than FAO/WHO permissible limits of plants (crop). Permissible limit not available (–).

The BiF of the metals per the rates were Al (1.14, 0.89, 0.81, 0.61), Cd (1.09, 1.85, 0.50, 0.13), Co (72.00, 58.81, 0.32, 0.23), Cr (1.25, 1.19, 0.78, 0.54), Cu (3.23, 4.18, 3.24, 1.95), Fe (0.23, 0.28, 0.24, 0.12), Ni (0.40, 0.66, 0.53, 0.13), Pb (0.42, 0.20, 0.20, 0.06), Zn (0.66, 6.81, 5.49, 4.98), and Mn (0.18, 3.71, 3.23, 2.47). These results showed that at the lowest rate, Al, Cd, Co, Cr, and Cu accumulated in the biomass, and there was less uptake of Fe, Ni, Pb, Zn, and Mn (BiF <1). When the rate of amendment was higher, the BiF of all the metals was less than 1 except Cu, Zn, and Mn, indicating uptake was limited to the latter three (Cu, Mn, and Zn), whereas the others were excluded. The data in Table 5 show that there was significant root production in the soil amended with the high SPS rate, and therefore, the BiF being less than 1 is an exclusion mechanism of cowpea, rather than the root becoming a limiting factor for the uptake.

In a study by Srivastava and Chopra (2014), cowpea was planted in soil irrigated with sugar mill effluent at different rates, and heavy metal accumulation in soil and tissues was determined. The results showed Zn, Cu, Ni, Cd, Cr, and Fe concentrations were high in the soil and in the tissues from the soil that received the highest irrigation amounts, agreeing with the data in Table 4. In a three-year study, Silva et al. (2013) repeatedly added tannery sludge compost to the soil and cultivated cowpea at the same rate as ours and a 20 t ha⁻¹. When metal accumulation was determined, only Cr accumulation was significant, and there was no translation to the grains. When the relationship between metals in the soil and in the seed was studied, most of them did not exceed the maximum permissible limit (Ismael et al., 2016) except Pb in the seeds. When the effects of metals (Zn, Fe, Cu, Cr, and Pb) on the growth were studied, Okon et al. (2023) reported that cowpea showed more tolerance compared to its counterpart, groundnut. These studies confirm the findings of our study that cowpea has a certain level of tolerance to metals and therefore lesser tissue accumulation (lower BiF, Table 4). Comparatively, our results further showed that tissue accumulation is dependent on the sources and the amounts of the metals in them. The combined soil and SPS content of metals was Pb>Fe>Zn>Cu>Al>others (Table 1), and some of these were the highest in the tissues.

Plant biomass production

The plant biomass produced (Table 5) reflected the significant changes in soil parameters (Table 2), soil nutrients (Table 3), and concentrations of metals (Table 4) measured. More plants were produced in the soil that received the highest SPS rate, where, in general, the soils were more fertile (high nutrients) with notably high SOM and SOC contents, agreeing with the findings of Lopes et al. (2020). Sewage sludge fertilization and cultivation of cowpea resulted in high vegetative growth and grain yield, and the results were related to improvements in SOM and nutrient mineralization. The tallest plants were from the soils amended with the higher amounts of the SPS, and that directly influenced the other plant growth parameters, leaf number, leaf length, and pod number (Table 5).

Table 5. Biomass production at different rates of amendments.

Plant parameters	Different rates of amendments (t ha ⁻¹)			
	0.00	2.5	5.00	10.00
Plants (number)	20.22±0.5 ^a	29.12±0.4 ^a	40.44±0.5 ^b	58.23±0.5 ^c
Height (cm)	148.33±0.2 ^a	198.24±0.2 ^b	224.67±0.6 ^c	299.33±0.5 ^{cd}
Leaf (weight, g)	42.23±0.0 ^a	58.25±0.2 ^b	60.33±0.2 ^{bc}	75.33±0.1 ^d
Leaf length (cm)	1.66±0.5 ^a	2.23±0.3 ^a	5.22±0.5 ^b	6.77±0.6 ^{bc}
Pods (number)	22.12±0.6 ^a	37.22±0.2 ^b	48.22±0.4 ^{bc}	64.77±0.9 ^d
Root (weight, g)	43.33±0.8 ^a	71.73±0.5 ^b	99.85±0.9 ^c	61.77±0.5 ^{bd}
Root length (cm)	15.22±0.1 ^a	19.33±0.2 ^a	26.33±0.9 ^b	32.67±0.7 ^{bc}
Root nodule (number)	7.12±0.3 ^a	10.14±0.3 ^a	16.55±0.6 ^b	36.55±0.7 ^c
Dry matter (g)	86.09±0.4 ^a	129.98±0.7 ^b	160.19±0.5 ^c	137.12±0.4 ^{bd}

The values are mean ± standard error of four replicates (n=4). The different letters within a row indicate statistical differences at p<0.05. Leaf and root weights are oven-dry weights.

The trend in root production was similar to the plant population, with more roots produced in the soil with the higher amendment rates, the increase being nearly 65–100%. The longer the roots, the more root nodules there were, and they were directly influenced by the greater availability of nutrients and improved soil conditions in the soil amended by higher SPS rates. In most soils, legume production is affected by soil biological, physical, and chemical properties, some of which were considered in this study are shown in the data tables. Soil nutrients, moisture, aeration, pH, nodule development (rhizobial symbiosis), and metal toxicity are known parameters that affect legume productivity (biomass production). The data showed that the general soil conditions (Table 4), nutrient status, and metal (Table 5) stresses directly affected the cowpea biomass production. There was a great improvement in the general soil conditions with moisture level ranging from 77–93%, pH was within normal range, and the total soil porosity was between 40–44 % (Table 4), and these reflected on the biomass production (Table 5).

Metal toxicity is an issue for the growth of plant roots, and a certain concentration of metals was available in the soil (Table 3). Despite that, the cowpea plants produced an increasing root biomass in the soils metal concentrations were high (Table 5). The mechanism for this seems to be the high level of cowpea's tolerance to environmental stresses (Langyintuo et al., 2003; Guerra et al., 2017) as pointed out previously. Metals such as Fe are used by legumes for nodule formation and development. The higher availability of Fe measured contributed to the increasing number of nodules with an increase in the rate of SPS (Brear et al., 2013). Araújo et al. (2007) studied the effects of composted textile sludge on growth, nodulation, and nitrogen fixation. The study showed no negative effects on nodule number and weight of the cowpea plants. Miranda et al. (2014) studied the effects of tannery sludge after five years of application on growth and nodulation of cowpea and reported that growth, nodulation, N accumulation, and yield increased by the highest amendment rates, similar to our results. Nodulation is an indicator of biological nitrogen fixation, and the increasing number of nodules recorded (Table 5) indicated that the presence of high concentrations of metals at the high amendment rates had minimal effects on the activities of rhizobia, similar to the findings of Santos et al. (2011). The concentrations of metals measured in cowpea biomass exceeded the standard permissible levels for legumes. However, since the soil originated from a residential area, many metal concentrations remained within permissible limits.

Conclusions

Disposal of SPS into the environment presents a significant concern in PNG. The potential for agricultural use as a management strategy was evaluated by cultivating cowpea. Changes in soil chemistry resulting from SPS amendment, along with plant biomass production and tissue accumulation of metals, were assessed in relation to soil health, agricultural productivity, and risks to livestock and human health. SPS amendment improved all measured parameters, including primary and secondary macronutrients and micronutrients. In most cases, soil and tissue metal concentrations, were dependent on the amendment rate, with the highest concentrations observed at 10 t ha⁻¹. Biomass production on a dry-matter basis also varied with amendment rate, with yields of 0.39, 0.58, 0.72, and 0.62 g m⁻². Although concerns remain regarding the presence of metals such as Cd, Ni, and Pb in soil and

Cr, Cu, and Pb in biomass, an amendment rate of 5.0 t ha⁻¹ appears optimal for increasing cowpea production while minimizing environmental pollution. These findings suggest that long-term environmental impacts of SPS application would be minimized if the 5.0 t ha⁻¹ rate is adopted.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no competing financial or personal interests that may appear to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability statement

All the data are included in the manuscript.

Author's contributions

Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, and Writing draft and editing: PM; Formal analysis, Data collection, analysis and investigation: LK. All authors read and approved the final draft.

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